

CONDUCTING EXPERIMENTS AND TESTS ON TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF CALCULATION METHODS THROUGH SOFTWARE-METHODOLOGICAL COMPLEXES AND ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

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Abstract. *The aim of this article is to improve the methodology of independent mastering of the subject of Calculation Methods by students through software and methodological complexes. In this experiment, test work was conducted on students of Namangan State University, Andijan State University and Gulistan State University, and it was found that the results of the students in the experiment increased by 11.9 percent compared to the results before the experiment.*

Keywords: *software and methodological complex, Calculation methods, independent learning.*

INTRODUCTION

Experimental and testing work was conducted to determine the effectiveness of our educational content developed for the mathematics program of higher education institutions and the " Calculation methods " course. The experimental work was carried out at Namangan State University, Gulistan State University, and Andijan State University in 2023-2026. A total of 526 students participated in the experimental work.

The experimental work was carried out in three stages:

1. Preparatory stage: 2023-2024 academic year.
2. Main stage: 2024-2025 academic year.
3. Final stage: 2025-2026 academic year.

Preparatory stage - at this stage, the relevance, goal, objectives, and object of the research were determined, the scientific, theoretical, and methodological foundations of the research problem were studied, the use of modern information and communication tools in the teaching and learning process of the "Computational Methods" course, and the creation of an information and educational environment were analyzed. The purpose of the experimental preparatory stage of the research work was to determine the level of use of modern information and communication technology tools in teaching the "Computational Methods" course taught in the mathematics department of universities, as well as the current state of teaching the "Computational Methods" course.

At the main stage, a software and methodological complex for the course "Methods of Calculation" taught in the mathematics department of universities was created, and the mathematics and applied mathematics departments of Namangan State University, Gulistan State University and Andijan State University were selected as experimental and testing sites, and experimental and testing work was carried out. Also, methodological instructions and textbooks

created for students to study the course "Methods of Calculation" were distributed. With the help of the experimental and testing work, the knowledge levels of students were determined.

The final stage - at this stage, work was carried out to edit the methodology developed to increase the effectiveness of the lesson in teaching the "Computational Methods" course through the software-methodical complex. The results of the pedagogical pilot-testing work on the use of the developed software-methodical complex and teaching the "Computational Methods" course were summarized, the conclusions were verified in practice, the results and materials obtained were systematized in accordance with the goals and objectives of the research.

Information about the experimental and control groups and the number of students					
№	Objects of experience	Groups	Number of students	Total	
1	Namangan State University	Experimental group	133	251	
		Control group	118		
2	Andijan State University	Experimental group	92	184	
		Control group	92		
3	Gulistan State University	Experimental group	46	91	
		Control group	45		
4	Total	Experimental group	271	526	
		Control group	255		

RESULTS

Experiment – results of test work and statistical analysis

Comparative table of statistical data from the experiment (among universities) on the development of pedagogical activity by improving the methodology of independent mastery of the subject of computational methods by students through software and methodological complexes.

Comparative table of statistical data before the experiment (by HEIs)					
№	An object of experience	High	Medium	Low	Total
Experimental group	Namangan State University	32	50	51	133
	Andijan State University	18	46	28	92
	Gulistan State University	13	19	14	46
	Total	63	115	93	271

Comparative table of statistical data before the experiment (by HEIs)

No	An object of experience	High	Medium	Low	Total
Control group	Namangan State University	24	54	40	118
	Andijan State University	25	38	29	92
	Gulistan State University	9	16	20	45
	Total	58	108	89	255

Now let's calculate these in percentage terms:

No	High	Medium	Low
Experimental group	23%	42%	34%

№	High	Medium	Low
Control group	23%	42%	35%

Comparative table of statistical data after the experiment on the development of pedagogical activity by improving the methodology of independent mastery of the subject of Computational Methods by students through software-methodological complexes (by universities).

№	An object of experience	High	Medium	Low	Total
Experimental group	Namangan State University	45	70	18	133
	Andijan State University	26	51	15	92
	Gulistan State University	14	25	7	46
	Total	85	146	40	271

Comparative table of statistical data after the experiment (by HEIs)

T/R	An object of experience	High	Medium	Low	Total
Control group	Namangan State University	38	48	32	118
	Andijan State University	19	52	21	92
	Gulistan State University	9	21	15	45
	Total	66	121	68	255

Now let's calculate these in percentage terms:

№	High	Medium	Low
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Experimental group	31%	54%	15%
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№	High	Medium	Low
Control group	26%	47%	27%

Comparative table of statistical data before the experiment (by HEIs)

Experimental group	5(High)	4(Medium)	3(Low)	Total
	63	115	93	n1=271

Number of students in the experimental group with the quality indicator Quality =63+115=178 people, we find them in percentage: $x = \frac{Quality \cdot 100\%}{n1} = \frac{178 \cdot 100\%}{271} = 65,6\%$

Control group	5(High)	4(Medium)	3(Low)	Total
	58	108	89	n2=255

Number of students in the control group with the quality indicator Quality =58+108=166 people, we find them in percentage: $x = \frac{Quality \cdot 100\%}{n2} = \frac{166 \cdot 100\%}{255} = 65,1\%$

So, the quality improvement in the experimental and control groups before the experiment is $(65.6-65.1) = 0.5\%$.

Comparative table of statistical data after the experiment (by HEIs)

Experimental group	5(High)	4(Medium)	3(Low)	Total
	85	146	40	m1=271

Number of students in the experimental group with the quality indicator Quality =85+146=231 people, we find them in percentage: $x = \frac{Quality \cdot 100\%}{m1} = \frac{231 \cdot 100\%}{271} = 85,2\%$

Control group	5(Yuqori)	4(O`rta)	3(Past)	Jami
	66	121	68	m2=255

Number of students in the control group with the quality indicator Quality =66+121=187 people, we find them in percentage: $x = \frac{Quality * 100\%}{m2} = \frac{187 * 100\%}{255} = 73,3\%$

So, the quality improvement in the experimental and control groups at the end of the experiment is (85.2-73.3) = 11.9%. This in turn means that the experimental and control groups are 11.9% more successful at the end of the experiment.

Comparison table of quality indicators before and after the experiment

Experimental group	
At the beginning of the experiment	65.6
After the experiment	85.2
Control group	
At the beginning of the experiment	65.1
After the experiment	73.3

Pedagogical experience - the effectiveness of test results is 11.9% higher x_i square (x_i^2) proved based on the criterion. Therefore, the average learning of students in the experimental group increased compared to the control group. In this case, we divide the students in the experimental and control groups into three categories:

- $i=1$ category – students who received a high (“5”) grade;
- $i=2$ category – students who received an average (“4”) grade;
- $i=3$ category – students who received a low (“3”) grade;

We introduce the following definitions by category:

- O_{1i} – the frequency of students in the experimental group who received grade i ;
- O_{2i} – the frequency of students in the test group who received grade i ;
- P_{1i} – the probability that a student randomly selected from the experimental group will receive grade i ;
- P_{2i} – the probability that a student randomly selected from the test group will receive grade i ;
- P_{1i} va P_{2i} The following hypotheses can be expressed through:
- $H_0: P_{1i} = P_{2i} \quad i=1,2,3;$

$H_1: P_{1i} \neq P_{2i}$ at least for some $i=1,2,3.$

If n_1 students participated in the experimental group and n_2 students participated in the control group, then the following random variable is taken as the test sample:

$$T = \frac{1}{n_1 n_2} \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{(n_1 * O_{2i} - n_2 * O_{1i})^2}{O_{1i} + O_{2i}}$$

T random variable degrees of freedom $\vartheta = 2$ was χ^2 has a distribution function. H_0 The rule for testing the hypothesis is as follows:

- Based on the data, the observed value of the T statistic is determined, which $T_{observe}$ defined as;

- $\alpha = 0,05$ and $\vartheta = 2$ degree of freedom χ^2 from the distribution table $T_{kr} = 1.67$ we find.

- If $T_{observe} < T_{kr}$ If so, the alternative hypothesis N_0 is accepted, otherwise α in terms of value N_0 is rejected and N_1 The alternative hypothesis is accepted.

If, based on the results of the experiments, hypothesis N_1 turns out to be correct, then it means that the experimental lessons conducted based on a special methodology have yielded results. According to the hypothesis testing rule, critical values are compared with the observed value of the criterion and calculations are performed based on the table.

The observed value of T at the beginning of the experiment is determined.

$$T_{observe} = \frac{1}{n_1 n_2} \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{(n_1 * O_{2i} - n_2 * O_{1i})^2}{O_{1i} + O_{2i}} \approx 1$$

χ^2 from the table of critical points of the distribution $\alpha = 0,05$ and $\vartheta = 2$ based on $T_{kr} = 1.67$ we define . According to the rule $T_{observe} < T_{kr}$ Since H_0 is the hypothesis, that is, there is no difference in the selected groups, is accepted.

The observed value of T at the end of the experiment is determined.

$$T_{observe} = \frac{1}{n_1 n_2} \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{(n_1 * O_{2i} - n_2 * O_{1i})^2}{O_{1i} + O_{2i}} \approx 11,9$$

χ^2 from the table of critical points of the distribution $\alpha = 0,05$ and $\vartheta = 2$ based on $T_{kr} = 1.67$ we define. According to the rule $T_{observe} < T_{kr}$ Therefore, the hypothesis N_0 is rejected, which means that the hypothesis H_1 is accepted. This means that, as we said above, the experimental testing is working. Pedagogical experience - the effectiveness of test results is 11.9% higher χ^2 square (χ^2 | 2) proved based on the criterion. In conclusion, the experimental and test work carried out to develop the pedagogical activity of students by improving the methodology for independent mastering of the subject of Computational Methods through software and methodological complexes shows that they have yielded effective results.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, in order to determine the level of effectiveness of the educational content of the software-methodological complex for the mathematics direction and the course "Methods of Calculation", the stages of organizing pedagogical experimental-test work and the work carried out at these stages were analyzed. Based on the above, the problems raised in the scientific research work showed the correctness of the hypothesis and the effectiveness of the solutions to the tasks set. The effectiveness of students' mastery was determined in the following:

- The use of multimedia technology increased students' interest in learning;
- The opportunity to master lectures and practical exercises together showed that students developed their knowledge and skills;
- Mastering the course on the basis of interactivity activated students' thinking abilities and increased the efficiency of mastering educational material;
- Conditions were created for students to quickly complete tasks such as reading, independent familiarization with educational materials, and analysis of information.

Mathematical statistical methods were used to determine the effectiveness of software and methodological complexes for the mathematics department of higher education institutions and the course "Computational Methods". After conducting an experimental test using traditional and remote methods, it was found that the indicators obtained in the experimental test group were higher than in the control group.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- It is necessary to widely introduce teaching methods using network technology in all areas of higher education institutions through a software-methodological complex;

- The software-methodological complex should include video lectures by leading and well-known specialists of leading higher education institutions in the subject "Computational Methods" and disciplines related to the field of mathematics;

- The results of the research can be used in all areas where the subject "Computational Methods" is taught, and other courses can be organized using the software-methodological complex.

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